

MORPHOLOGY OF LYMPH NODES IN PATIENTS AFTER EMERGENCY NEPHRECTOMY.

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Relevance of the topic: The study of morphological changes in lymph nodes in patients after emergency nephrectomy is one of the important scientific and practical tasks in medicine today. Nephrectomy is a surgical procedure performed due to tumors and other formations, chronic renal failure and other pathologies, which can lead to changes in the immune system. This is likely to manifest itself in reactive and pathological changes in lymphoid tissues, and lymph nodes play a key role in immune control, as well as participate in the formation of tumor and inflammatory reactions.

Thus, the study of the morphology of lymph nodes after emergency nephrectomy is scientifically and clinically important, it helps to identify pathogenetic mechanisms of adaptation of the organism, to determine diagnostic and prognostic criteria, as well as to optimize treatment and rehabilitation methods.

Purpose of the study: The purpose of the study was to study the morphological changes in lymph nodes in patients who applied to the Khorezm branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Center of Urology, depending on the etiology of emergency nephrectomy and various subsequent diseases, the nature of compensatory-adaptive processes.

Results: During the study, out of 10 patients who applied to the Khorezm branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Center of Urology during the current year, 8 patients underwent emergency nephroectomy, and 2 were recommended for hemodialysis treatment. When the lymph nodes of the patients who underwent nephroectomy were examined pathologically, hyperplasia of the lymph nodes was detected in 2 of the 8 patients, fibrotic changes in the lymph nodes in 2, and granulomatous changes in the lymph nodes in 4.

Conclusions: In conclusion, it can be said that pathological examination of lymph nodes in patients after emergency nephrectomy is important in assessing the general condition of the patient and the extent of the disease. In addition, in order to

prevent the disease, it is important to adhere to a healthy lifestyle, undergo regular medical examinations, and avoid harmful factors.

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